

Speculation on Gibbs' Paradox Part 4

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 29, 2026

In Part 3, we argued that both the MaxEnt (maximization of entropy subject to constraints) approach of obtaining the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution and the Sackur-Tetrode entropy equation (for identical particles) requires the use of the first order Stirling's approximation: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$. In a classical ideal gas, one deals with an Avogadro's number 6×10^{23} of particles and so the first order approximation is warranted. It is this approximation which gives rise to extensivity of entropy of an ideal gas. A full calculation, not using an approximation does not yield extensivity as argued in Part 3.

In the literature (1), a Fermi gas distribution is applied to much smaller systems of particles with good experimental success. For example, heavy ion collisions between selenium-selenium or gold-gold nuclei could create a hot ideal gas like system. In such a case, there are selenium isotopes with 82 nucleons, suggesting 164 hot nucleons in a Fermi gas. Under certain circumstances a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution might be used and so the volume part of the entropy should still behave as $-k \ln(V^N / N!)$, so one has $N \ln(N)$ from the denominator (associated with nucleon number). A third order Stirling's approximation yields $\ln(N!) = N \ln(N) - N + \sqrt{2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot N}$ or $836.4 - 164 + 32$. In such a case, the third term (which breaks extensivity of an ideal gas) represents a 4.5% correction due to the last term. Although this is not huge, it is not insignificant either and indicates that with these numbers one is seeing a break with the extensivity of an ideal gas (which is an approximation following from the use of $\ln(N!) = N \ln(N)$.)

One may also consider results for gold (197 nucleons) and lead (204) nucleons. We use an atom with 200 nucleons i.e. $N = 400$ in a two ion system as an example. $\ln(N!) \approx 2396.6 - 400 + 50.1$ yields a third term per cent of about 2.4% which again is small, but not negligible.

As a result, we argue that our conclusion about the Sackur-Tetrode equation for entropy being an approximation (and hence extensivity of entropy for an ideal gas also being an approximation) holds because one uses the first order Stirling's approximation. It does not hold if one uses the approximation up to third order (nor does it hold for the exact expression). We show here that the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor is sometimes applied to systems with particles on the order of 164 or 400 and that in these cases, one can see the breaking of extensivity of entropy to a small degree.

Ideal Gas Extensivity is an Approximation

The well-known Gibb's paradox for ensuring extensivity of ideal gas entropies, i.e. treating particles as identical and using:

$$\ln(V^N / N!) \quad (1)$$

is based on a very strong approximation, namely the use of the first order Stirling's approximation:

$$\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) \quad ((2))$$

To third order the approximation is (3):

$$\ln(N!) = n \ln(n) - n + \sqrt{2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot n} \quad ((3))$$

In a typical ideal gas, one has about 6×10^{23} particles (Avogadro's number) and so the first order approximation ((1)) is very accurate even though it is a drastic approximation, i.e.

$$N! = N \text{ power } N \quad ((4))$$

Furthermore, the first order Stirling's approximation is used to derive the MB distribution $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

In the literature (1), a Fermi distribution is used to describe physical systems with as few as 164 or 200 particles. In a high temperature approximate ideal gas picture, the volume entropy should still be linked to:

$$-\ln(V \text{ power } N / N!) \quad ((5))$$

We suggest that one may consider an ideal gas law in certain cases of relativistic heavy-ion collisions (3). In other words, one may see how the first order Stirling's approximation is not sufficient.

We note that the first order Stirling's approximation $\ln(N!) = N \ln(N)$ and $\ln(N!) = N \ln(N) - N$, both yield the same Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution because in Maxent $-n(e_i) \rightarrow -dn(e_i)$ and there is already a Lagrange multiplier associated with $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. Note: $n(e_i) = Np(e_i)$. Furthermore, the second term $-n$ in Stirling's approximation does not break extensivity, it is only the third term which does. That being said, it seems that the ideal gas approximation may be applied to a high energy collision of selenium, lead or gold atoms. If this is the case, one may quantitatively see to what extent extensivity is broken.

Heavy Ion Collisions

We consider the effect of a third order term in Stirling's approximation which breaks extensivity of entropy.

For the case of two Selenium with 82 nucleons (a particular isotope), one has 164 nucleons in a colliding system.

$$\ln(N!) = N \ln(N) - N + \sqrt{2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot N} \text{ or } 836.4 - 164 + 32. \text{ In such a case, the third term (which breaks extensivity of an ideal gas) represents a 4.5\% correction} \quad ((6))$$

Gold has about 197 nucleons (a particular isotope) and lead, 204. We use 200 for a representative ion and so $N = 400$:

$\ln(N!) \approx 2396.6 - 400 + 50.1$ yields a third term per cent of about 2.4% which again is small, but not negligible. ((7))

The point we make is that one may be able to use the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Sackur-Tetrode formalism in systems of rather small numbers of particles. In such a case, one may actually see a small break with the notion of extensivity of entropy.

We note that descriptions of multifragmentation based on describing two heavy colliding ions as a Fermi gas match experiment well.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part 3, we argued that extensivity of an ideal gas only follows due to the drastic first order Stirling's approximation: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ or $n! = n$ power n . It does not follow if one uses the full expression $-\ln(V^N / N!)$ nor does it follow if one uses the Stirling's approximation to third order: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) - n + \sqrt{2\pi n}$. For a typical classical ideal gas, n is of the order of 6×10^{23} and so the first order Stirling's approximation is very good. Thus, entropy extensivity is an approximation, but a good one with such a large number of particles.

Here we argue that a Fermi gas model is applied in the literature (1), to heavy high energy colliding atoms like gold (200 nucleons for a particular isotope). If one considers the high temperature one might consider how an ideal gas with this number of particles $N=400$ breaks entropy extensivity. One may see the beginnings of a small breakdown in that the third order correction is about 2.8%.

References

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